

ORIGINAL RESEARCH**Investigating the vowel mispronunciation of undergraduate students of the Faculty of Management and Commerce, South Eastern University of Sri Lanka**Rifka Nusrath.GM^{1*}, Abdul Halik.AF²¹ DELT, South Eastern University of Sri Lanka² T/Mu/Al Hilal Central College, New Jetty Road, Mutur, Trincomalee, Sri Lanka**Correspondence**

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the vowel mispronunciation of undergraduate students of the Faculty of Management and Commerce, South Eastern University of Sri Lanka. The aim of this study was to identify the problems and difficulties faced by the students in pronouncing vowel sounds in their loud reading and speaking, and the factors which affects students' pronunciation development. It has been observed that learners encounter number of pronunciation problems and difficulties in speaking and loud reading. In this study, fifty 2nd year Students of the Faculty of Management and Commerce, South Eastern University of Sri Lanka were randomly selected as sample population for investigation. The primary data were collected using qualitative and quantitative methods, and the research instruments used in this study were oral pronunciation test, questionnaire and audio tape recording. The instruments enabled the researcher to identify vowel mispronunciation with their opinions about pronunciation. According to the data analysis, the findings show that the learners encountered difficulties in pronouncing vowel sounds such as /i:/ as /i/, /u:/ as /u/ and /əʊ/ as /o/. Moreover, the opinion survey revealed that the learners show lack of interest in learning pronunciation and many factors that affect their pronunciation development. These pronunciation problems and difficulties can be overcome and improved through implementing pronunciation as a separate component like grammar and writing in English as a Second Language curriculum of Department of English Language Teaching of South Eastern University of Sri Lanka.

Key words: English as a Second Language; mispronunciation; South Eastern University of Sri Lanka; undergraduate

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1.Introduction

Pronunciation of a language seems to be a very significant part to expose a language and convey ideas in oral communication clearly. But nonnative speakers of English who learn English as a second language (L2) or foreign language (FL) find a lot of difficulties in acquiring correct pronunciation. In this sense, Garcia (2007) says that English pronunciation is one of the most difficult skills to acquire and learners should spend lots of time improving their pronunciation. It is the problem not only in Sri Lanka but also in many Asian countries since there are fewer similarities between their first language (L1) and English Language.

However, in every country, English is being learned as L1, L2, or FL around the world. Therefore, more prominence has to be given to learning English and developing learners'

speaking ability with pronunciation, because it is a global language. In Sri Lanka, English is being learned as a second language and in most educational institutions. English is taught as either a main or optional subject. Pronunciation challenges are a common problem among most ESL learners in Sri Lanka. As a result, the pronunciation was focused on investigating the problems and difficulties faced by ESL learners of Faculty of Management and Commerce at South Eastern University of Sri Lanka. Not only at the Faculty of Management and Commerce but also at other educational institutions such as private colleges, and schools, the learners have been reported to encounter numerous difficulties and problems in both speaking and pronunciation, since the very little emphasis is given for listening and speaking skills in the